

CYCLOPES - Fighting Cybercrime – Law Enforcement Practitioners’ Network

Deliverable 6.13 Policy Paper on Ethical Framework for Cybercrime Investigations – with a special focus on AI-facilitated investigations

Public

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1. Summary

The focus of this Deliverable D6.13 is to shed light on some of the most relevant ethics frameworks related to Cybercrime investigations, where Law Enforcement Agencies utilize AI-based investigation tools. This policy paper does not provide an exhaustive overview but puts the focus on *ethics* frameworks that have been analysed and discussed as part of the ongoing work of the CYCLOPES project. It does – aside from the draft AI Act - especially not elaborate upon the existing *legal* frameworks. Despite harmonization approaches (such as through the Council of Europe Convention on Cybercrime) Cybercrime, investigations are largely regulated by differing national legal standards. Although such legal standards do partly codify ethics standards, they are not covered by this policy paper.

The overview highlights, that the recommendations from the High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence that were published in 2019 were actually only the start of an on-going process of developing a robust ethics framework for AI, that does impact the work of law enforcement agencies. The 2022 Accountability Principles for AI (AP4AI) and the draft AI Act are examples for important building blocks related to the ethics framework. CYCLOPES will continue to follow the developments and engage in an exchange with the law enforcement community to discuss the community's perspective if the framework is sufficient or requires adjustments.

2. About CYCLOPES

The HORIZON 2020 project CYCLOPES (Fighting Cybercrime – Law Enforcement Practitioners Network) aims to build a stable European network of law enforcement agencies to effectively combat cybercrime. It is a five-year network project with 20 partners from 14 different EU countries. The partners come from EU law enforcement agencies, research institutes, universities and companies. The lead lies with the Polish Platform for Homeland Security (PPHS). The project started in May 2021.

Objectives of the project are:

- the identification of priorities for standardization;
- recommendations for innovation uptake and implementation;
- social, ethical and legal reports providing guidance and training suggestions for cybercrime investigators;
- dissemination of results through workshops, conferences, webinars, publications, policy papers and media.

Work Package 7 focuses on ethics and legal issues. The partners involved in WP7 are among other issues analysing legal and ethical issues related to Cybercrime and Cybercrime investigations (Task T7.2). The partners submitted a comprehensive assessment of legal and ethical issues in month M12 (Deliverable 7.6) and are currently working on the first update (due in month M28).

3. Setting the scene – Cybercrime

The Internet has become even more established as a crime scene in the course of the Covid pandemic in 2020 during which government-mandated lockdowns forced many people to work online from home. The pandemic has also shown that perpetrators are able to adapt effectively to new social circumstances because they have very quickly developed new narratives for their business models (phishing emails with a Covid 19 theme to commit cyber fraud), particularly related to the Covid environment. From the statistics it is clear that in areas such as shoplifting or burglary, the number of crimes has decreased, while the number of crimes committed using the Internet as a tool for crime (in Germany) has increased by 8.7%.¹

Europol currently sees four focal points in the area of cybercrime: In addition to (1) ransomware attacks, these are (2) child abuse, (3) malware for mobile devices, and (4) so-called CEO fraud, in which criminals pose as the boss of a company via E-mail or their simulated voice and ask subordinates to transfer money.² A large number of cybercrimes are now committed through the use of new automated technologies, which in turn leads to a greater number of offenses and thus to an aggravation of the challenges for investigating authorities. Cyberattacks based on AI systems is a growing trend identified by the European Cybercrime Centre (EC3) of EUROPOL in its Internet Crime Threat Assessment Report 2020.³ When criminals teach their AI systems to attack a victim's systems, it causes the attack to be faster and more sophisticated than attacks done manually by human individuals.⁴ In particular, the AI-tool ChatGPT, which was launched in November 2022, poses great risks of being used by criminals. It may offer criminals new opportunities, especially for crimes involving social engineering, given its abilities to respond to messages in context and adopt a specific writing style in order to deceive the addressees.⁵

4. Evolution Artificial Intelligence (AI)

Historically, the term Artificial Intelligence refers to a broad field of research within computer science, which was founded as early as 1956 in the USA under the name Artificial Intelligence (Dartmouth Proposal).⁶ Since its foundation, the field has experienced multiple cycles of exaggerated expectations and subsequent disillusionment. The leap from research to business and everyday life was achieved, at the latest, in the 1970s and 1980s with the development of so-called expert systems.⁷ The definition of AI suggested by the European Commission in 2018 was the following: "artificial intelligence (AI) refers to systems that display intelligent behaviour

¹ *Palmowski*, Corona Effects for Statistics on Criminal Cases, WISTA 2022, p. 52.

² Interview with Philipp Ammann (Europol), Deutschlandfunk, 19.07.2021.

³ INTERPOL, Internet Crime Assessment Report 2020 (IOCTA 2020 Report), p. 18, available at: <https://www.europol.europa.eu/activities-services/main-reports/internet-organised-crime-threat-assessment-iocta-2020>.

⁴ Artificial intelligence security threat, crime and forensic: IEEE Access 2020, 8.

⁵ Chat GPT: The Impact of Large Language Models on Law Enforcement, EUROPOL Tech Watch, 27.03.2023.

⁶ Proposal for the Dartmouth Sommer Research Project on Artificial Intelligence, Mc Carthy, Minsky, Rochester/Shannon 1955.

⁷ Expert opinion of the Data Ethics Commission, Artificial Intelligence, p.59, available: https://www.bmi.bund.de/SharedDocs/downloads/DE/publikationen/themen/it-digitalpolitik/gutachten-datenethikkommission.pdf?__blob=publicationFile&v=7.

by analyzing their environment and taking actions – with some degree of autonomy – to achieve specific goals.⁸ Today, AI is used in all areas of life (e.g., healthcare, finance and logistics) and simplifies a wide range of processes and actions. As noted in section 3. above, AI is also increasingly being used as an effective means of committing cybercrime, while also providing a necessary means of combating cybercrime. It is making investigators task of analysis faster and causes less costs. Machine Learning can be applied not only to reveal crimes, it can even predict crime hotspots.⁹ In addition to the technical and legal issues involved in the usage of AI as an investigation and research tool, the issues of ethics are also important, especially in criminal profiling based on information revealed about a group or an individual.¹⁰ From the investigators point of view, ethical issues are often experienced as a “moral or ethical dilemma” that they have to face in the course of cybercrime investigations.¹¹

5. Ethics Frameworks

Within the context of Work Package WP7, the partners involved have especially analysed the range of ethics frameworks evolved so far.¹² As pointed out before, the number is not exhaustive. In April 2020, the “AI Ethics Guidelines Global Inventory” run by the initiative “Algorithm Watch” counted more than 170 different entries from all over the world.¹³

5.1 Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI¹⁴

The High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence (H-LEG on AI)¹⁵ was an independent organisation established by the European Commission to explore how to uphold in the face of AI the indivisible and universal values of human dignity, freedom, equality and solidarity as well as the rule of law upon which the EU is founded.¹⁶ The principles elaborated in this context are also applicable to the use of AI as an investigative tool for LEAs.

In April 2019, the H-LEG on AI published “Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI”¹⁷ which aim to provide guidance on identifying and maintaining the EU’s foundational values in the context of AI. Based on the approach of fundamental rights, the most abstract layer identifies as foundation seven ethical principles that must be respected in any development and deployment of AI systems:

⁸ Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the European Council, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions on Artificial Intelligence for Europe, Brussels, 25.4.2018 COM(2018) 237 final.

⁹ Comparison of machine Learning Algorithms for Predicting Crime Hotspots, Zhang, Liu, Xiau, IEEE 2020, 8.

¹⁰ Cyber Crime Investigation: Landscape, Challenges, and Future Research Directions, Horan/Saiedian, Cybersecurity and Privacy, p.593.

¹¹ Cyber Crime Investigation: Landscape, Challenges, and Future Research Directions, Horan/Saiedian, Cybersecurity and Privacy, p.594.

¹² For more information see: Deliverable 7.6.

¹³ Algorithm Watch, AI Ethics Global Inventory available: <https://inventory.algorithmwatch.org/about>.

¹⁴ AI H-LEG, “Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI”, 8 April 2019, https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/dae/document.cfm?doc_id=60419.

¹⁵ <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/high-level-expert-group-artificial-intelligence>.

¹⁶ Second paragraph of the Preamble of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union (EU-Charter), 26 October 2012, 2012/C 326/02.

¹⁷ AI H-LEG, Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI, 8 April 2019, https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/dae/document.cfm?doc_id=60419.

- human agency and oversight,¹⁸
- technical robustness and safety,¹⁹
- privacy and data governance,²⁰
- transparency,²¹
- diversity, non-discrimination and fairness,²²
- societal and environmental wellbeing²³ and
- accountability.²⁴

Developers and users of AI systems are expected to implement and apply these seven requirements to their development processes, while deployers should ensure that their products and services meet these requirements and end-users should be informed accordingly and enabled to request that they are maintained.²⁵

For each of the seven key principles the Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI provide a concrete and non-exhaustive list of requirements that must be adjusted to the specific case.²⁶ In July 2020, the H-LEG on AI published the final version of this list as “Assessment List for Trustworthy AI” (ALTAI).²⁷ This list is intended for self-evaluation purposes and aims to invoke appropriate behaviour and caring for an organisational culture committed to the protection of fundamental rights as laid down in the EU Treaties and the EU Charter.²⁸ This means for investigators that they must regularly review and reflect on whether the AI-based technology they use complies or has complied with these ethical principles in each individual case. Establishing the trustworthiness of AI systems requires investigators who act responsibly when using them. Acting responsibly means accepting moral integrity and authenticity as ideals and doing everything possible to achieve them. This is all the more important because some fundamental rights and correlated principles are absolute (e.g. human dignity) while others offer more flexibility and yet, in a typical investigational scenario they all have to be brought

¹⁸ AI H-LEG, Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI, 8 April 2019, p. 15, https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/dae/document.cfm?doc_id=60419.

¹⁹ AI H-LEG, “Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI”, 8 April 2019, p. 16, https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/dae/document.cfm?doc_id=60419.

²⁰ AI H-LEG, “Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI”, 8 April 2019, p. 17, https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/dae/document.cfm?doc_id=60419.

²¹ AI H-LEG, “Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI”, 8 April 2019, p. 18, https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/dae/document.cfm?doc_id=60419.

²² AI H-LEG, “Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI”, 8 April 2019, p. 18, https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/dae/document.cfm?doc_id=60419.

²³ AI H-LEG, “Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI”, 8 April 2019, p. 19, https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/dae/document.cfm?doc_id=60419.

²⁴ AI H-LEG, “Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI”, 8 April 2019, p. 19, https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/dae/document.cfm?doc_id=60419.

²⁵ AI H-LEG, “Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI”, 8 April 2019, p. 14, https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/dae/document.cfm?doc_id=60419.

²⁶ AI H-LEG, “Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI”, 8 April 2019, pp. 24-31, https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/dae/document.cfm?doc_id=60419.

²⁷ High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence (AI H-LEG), Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence (ALTAI), 17 July 2020.

²⁸ High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence (AI H-LEG), Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence (ALTAI), 17 July 2020, p. 3-4.

into an appropriate equilibrium.²⁹ Therefore, ethical dilemmas and trade-offs need to be approached via reasoned and evidence-based reflection.³⁰ The above listed seven fundamental ethical principles identified in the Ethical Guidelines for Trusted AI of the H-LEG on AI provide the framework for the moral integrity that a society should continually strive for in its use of information technology. Every user of AI should be reasonable and trustworthy in terms of the seven key requirements developed by H-LEG on AI.

5.2 Accountability Principles for Artificial Intelligence (AP4AI) in the Internal Security Domain

AP4AI is a project coordinated by the Europol Innovation Lab and CENTRIC (Centre of Excellence in Terrorism, Resilience, Intelligence and Organized Crime Research). In this project, the results of large-scale surveys served as the basis for the principles of accountability. The principles elaborated in the course of the AP4AI project are particularly suitable for investigative authorities that create or use AI as an investigation tool. Within the AP4AI project, more than 5,500 answers from citizens have been collected. This citizen consultation offers important insights for the further work of AP4AI and the perception of AI use by internal security practitioners more generally.³¹ Analysis of the citizens answers revealed that also citizens recognise a great potential in AI use for safeguarding vulnerable groups and society. The majority of citizens took the view that AI should be used to detect criminals and criminal organizations and 78,6 % of the respondents were in favour of AI predicting crimes before they happen.³²

AP4AI strives towards an AI Accountability Agreement (AAA) that specifies formal and implementable processes for the application of the Accountability Principles for different uses of AI within the internal security domain.³³ The AAA is envisioned as a social contract between internal security organizations and its stakeholders including citizens, oversight bodies, suppliers, consumers of AI services and others as applicable.³⁴ To achieve this, the AAA must include, as a baseline, these four components: (1) context, (2) scope, (3) methodology, and (4) accountability governance.

The AP4AI framework consists two core elements:

- the 12 accountability principles, and
- application guidelines for their implementation to operational environments.³⁵

²⁹ AI H-LEG, “Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI”, 8 April 2019, p. 13, https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/dae/document.cfm?doc_id=60419.

³⁰ AI H-LEG, “Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI”, 8 April 2019, p. 20, https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/dae/document.cfm?doc_id=60419.

³¹ https://www.ap4ai.eu/sites/default/files/2022-03/AP4AI_Framework_Blueprint_22Feb2022.pdf (p. 7).

³² https://www.ap4ai.eu/sites/default/files/2022-03/AP4AI_Framework_Blueprint_22Feb2022.pdf (p. 7).
³³ https://www.ap4ai.eu/sites/default/files/2022-03/AP4AI_Framework_Blueprint_22Feb2022.pdf (p.59).

³⁴ https://www.ap4ai.eu/sites/default/files/2022-03/AP4AI_Framework_Blueprint_22Feb2022.pdf (p.59).

³⁵ https://www.ap4ai.eu/sites/default/files/2022-03/AP4AI_Framework_Blueprint_22Feb2022.pdf (p. 57).

These are the 12 Accountability Principles³⁶ with abbreviated description: **legality**³⁷ (the use of AI should be lawful and governed by formal, promulgated rules in any aspect); **universality**³⁸ (provides that all relevant aspects of AI deployments within the internal security community are covered through the accountability process); **pluralism**³⁹ (ensures that oversight involves all relevant stakeholders engaged in and affected by a specific AI deployment); **transparency**⁴⁰ (is a principle that involves making available clear, accurate and meaningful information about AI processes, decisions, technologies, capabilities and specific deployments pertinent for assessing and enforcing accountability); **independence**⁴¹ (the oversight body should be independent from individuals and organisations involved in the use of AI including the design, development, supply and deployment); **commitment to robust evidence**⁴² (evidence in this sense refers to documented records or other proof of compliance measures in respect of legal and other formal obligations pertaining to the use of AI in an internal security context); **enforceability and redress**⁴³ (requires that relevant oversight bodies and enforcement authorities have access to the necessary powers, means and mechanisms to respond appropriately to instances of non-compliance with applicable obligations by those deploying AI in a criminal justice context); **compellability**⁴⁴ (refers to the need for competent authorities and oversight bodies to compel those deploying or using AI in the internal security community to provide access to necessary information, systems or individuals by creating formal obligations in this regard); **explainability**⁴⁵ (requires those using AI to ensure that information about this use is provided in a meaningful way that is accessible and easily understood by the relevant participants and audiences); **constructiveness**⁴⁶ (comprises the idea of participating in a constructive dialogue with relevant stakeholders involved in the use of AI and other interested parties, by engaging with and responding positively to various inputs); **conduct**⁴⁷ (requires that AI practices should always be able to stand up to scrutiny by the public and other bodies, by adhering to sector-specific principles,

³⁶ For a brief overview see: [https://www.europol.europa.eu/cms/sites/default/files/documents/Accountability Principles for Artificial Intelligence AP4AI in the Internet Security Domain.pdf](https://www.europol.europa.eu/cms/sites/default/files/documents/Accountability_Principles_for_Artificial_Intelligence_AP4AI_in_the_Internet_Security_Domain.pdf) (Table 3), where the meaning of each principle is explained in connection to the respective principle.
³⁷ [https://www.ap4ai.eu/sites/default/files/2022-03/AP4AI Framework Blueprint 22Feb2022.pdf](https://www.ap4ai.eu/sites/default/files/2022-03/AP4AI_Framework_Blueprint_22Feb2022.pdf) (p. 66 et seq.).
³⁸ [https://www.ap4ai.eu/sites/default/files/2022-03/AP4AI Framework Blueprint 22Feb2022.pdf](https://www.ap4ai.eu/sites/default/files/2022-03/AP4AI_Framework_Blueprint_22Feb2022.pdf) (p. 70 et seq.).
³⁹ [https://www.ap4ai.eu/sites/default/files/2022-03/AP4AI Framework Blueprint 22Feb2022.pdf](https://www.ap4ai.eu/sites/default/files/2022-03/AP4AI_Framework_Blueprint_22Feb2022.pdf) (p. 73 et seq.).
⁴⁰ [https://www.ap4ai.eu/sites/default/files/2022-03/AP4AI Framework Blueprint 22Feb2022.pdf](https://www.ap4ai.eu/sites/default/files/2022-03/AP4AI_Framework_Blueprint_22Feb2022.pdf) (p. 75 et seq.).
⁴¹ [https://www.ap4ai.eu/sites/default/files/2022-03/AP4AI Framework Blueprint 22Feb2022.pdf](https://www.ap4ai.eu/sites/default/files/2022-03/AP4AI_Framework_Blueprint_22Feb2022.pdf) (p. 78 et seq.).
⁴² [https://www.ap4ai.eu/sites/default/files/2022-03/AP4AI Framework Blueprint 22Feb2022.pdf](https://www.ap4ai.eu/sites/default/files/2022-03/AP4AI_Framework_Blueprint_22Feb2022.pdf) (p. 80 et seq.).
⁴³ [https://www.ap4ai.eu/sites/default/files/2022-03/AP4AI Framework Blueprint 22Feb2022.pdf](https://www.ap4ai.eu/sites/default/files/2022-03/AP4AI_Framework_Blueprint_22Feb2022.pdf) (p. 82 et seq.).
⁴⁴ [https://www.ap4ai.eu/sites/default/files/2022-03/AP4AI Framework Blueprint 22Feb2022.pdf](https://www.ap4ai.eu/sites/default/files/2022-03/AP4AI_Framework_Blueprint_22Feb2022.pdf) (p. 85 et seq.).
⁴⁵ [https://www.ap4ai.eu/sites/default/files/2022-03/AP4AI Framework Blueprint 22Feb2022.pdf](https://www.ap4ai.eu/sites/default/files/2022-03/AP4AI_Framework_Blueprint_22Feb2022.pdf) (p. 87 et seq.).
⁴⁶ [https://www.ap4ai.eu/sites/default/files/2022-03/AP4AI Framework Blueprint 22Feb2022.pdf](https://www.ap4ai.eu/sites/default/files/2022-03/AP4AI_Framework_Blueprint_22Feb2022.pdf) (p. 89 et seq.).
⁴⁷ [https://www.ap4ai.eu/sites/default/files/2022-03/AP4AI Framework Blueprint 22Feb2022.pdf](https://www.ap4ai.eu/sites/default/files/2022-03/AP4AI_Framework_Blueprint_22Feb2022.pdf) (p. 91 et seq.).

professional standards and expected behaviours relating to conduct within a role, which incorporate integrity and ethical considerations); and **learning organization**⁴⁸ (promotes the willingness and ability of organisations and people to improve AI in every respect through the application of (new) knowledge and insights).

For each of these 12 principles, the Accountability Framework explains the meaning, examples of applicable legislations, an individual implementation guide and operational considerations for the organization. All principles emanate from ethics and have an impact on privacy, data management and data protection. Overall, the Accountability Framework is a very specific and practical guidance that can assist investigative agencies in using AI in a privacy-compliant manner. Furthermore, it offers approaches to ensure that the work with AI in law enforcement environment becomes more effective and goal-oriented. Not dissimilar to the system of principles elaborated by the H-LEG on AI, the Accountability Framework expresses the system of ethics principles specific to the official mandate of law enforcement ecosystem. As such both require evening out fundamental rights and values in a constant equilibrium.

5.3 Draft Artificial Intelligence Act (Draft EU AI Act) as a Future Legislation

In April 2021, the European Commission presented its proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council laying down harmonized rules for artificial intelligence (AI), also known as the AI Regulation. The draft legislation of the EU AI Act was preceded by non-binding guidelines, such as the already mentioned "Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI" and the "White Paper on Artificial Intelligence"⁴⁹. Since 2021, the EU legislator has been working on the regulatory framework for AI to protect fundamental (privacy) and consumer rights from the risks posed by AI. The Draft EU AI Act is envisioned as a risk-based approach to regulating artificial intelligence in the EU.⁵⁰ The proposed regulation for AI intends to achieve following specific objectives: (i) ensure that AI systems are safe and respect existing law on fundamental rights and Union values; (ii) ensure legal certainty; (iii) enhance governance and effective enforcement of existing law on fundamental rights and safety; (iv) facilitate the development of a single market for lawful, safe and trustworthy AI applications.⁵¹ The Draft EU AI Act sets harmonised rules for the development, placement and use of AI systems in the EU. The Draft EU AI Act takes into account that AI systems differ by characteristic and risk and includes prohibitions and a conformity assessment system adapted from EU product safety law.

The balanced and proportionate horizontal approach of the Draft EU AI Act is risk-based and distinguishes four risk categories: (1) unacceptable risks, (2) high risks, (3) limited risks and

⁴⁸ https://www.ap4ai.eu/sites/default/files/2022-03/AP4AI_Framework_Blueprint_22Feb2022.pdf (p. 93 et seq.).

⁴⁹ Whitepaper 1, Cybersecurity and Ethics, 2020, available: <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e5b5a59615&appId=PPGMS>.

⁵⁰ Commission, Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council laying down harmonized rules on artificial intelligence (Artificial Intelligence Act) and amending certain Union legislative acts, COM(2021) 206 final, 21 April 2021.

⁵¹ Commission, Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council laying down harmonized rules on artificial intelligence (Artificial Intelligence Act) and amending certain Union legislative acts, COM(2021) 206 final, 21 April 2021, p. 3.

(4) minimal risks.⁵² The Draft EU AI Act's risk methodology reveals that the requirements for trustworthy AI are a crucial feature for AI systems in the EU. This human-centric approach reflects the criteria elaborated in the H-LEG's "Ethical Guidelines for Trustworthy AI"⁵³ and enshrines them in appropriate and specific legal requirements. After the proposal of the Draft EU AI Act by the Commission in April 2021, the Council adopted its General Approach in December 2022 leaving it for Parliament to adopt its position and initiate the trilogue phase of the ordinary legislative procedure (COD). The *Committee on Internal Market and Consumer Protection* (IMCO) and the *Committee on Civil Liberties, Justice and Home Affairs* (LIBE) presented their joint Draft Report in Parliament in April 2022 suggesting more than three hundred amendments (Amended AI Act) to the Artificial Intelligence Act.⁵⁴ This initial Draft Report has received more than 3,000 suggested amendments which currently are being considered.⁵⁵ Once the joint Committees have adopted their Final Report, the full plenum of Parliament will take a vote on it and adopt its position for the negotiations in the trilogue which is currently expected to begin in summer 2023 and focus on the definition of AI, the classifications of risks and the obligations of an AI system's user.

Against this background, the EU AI Act is unlikely to come into force before 2024. The future EU AI Act will, once in force, then become applicable after a transition period of two years⁵⁶ and will also apply to law enforcement agencies using AI-tools to fulfil their mandate. Therefore, the development and use of AI tools in the law enforcement ecosystem has to comply with the strict requirements of the future EU AI Act.

⁵² Commission, Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council laying down harmonized rules on artificial intelligence (Artificial Intelligence Act) and amending certain Union legislative acts, COM(2021) 206 final, 21 April 2021, 5.2.2.

⁵³ AI H-LEG, "Ethical Guidelines for Trustworthy AI", 8 April 2019.

⁵⁴ European Parliament, Draft Report on the proposal for a regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on harmonised rules on Artificial Intelligence (Artificial Intelligence Act) and amending certain Union Legislative Acts (COM2021/0206 – C9-0146/2021 – 2021/0106(COD)), 20 April 2022 by Rapporteur: Brando Benifei and Ioan-Dragoş Tudorache suggesting 309 amendments to the Artificial Intelligence Act.

⁵⁵ See: <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/legislative-train/theme-a-europe-fit-for-the-digital-age/file-regulation-on-artificial-intelligence> (last visited on 18 February 2023).

⁵⁶ Art. 85(2) Draft EU AI Act.